

Sample 18a

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0010
	{Si}	68.1
	{Al, Si}	8.2
	{Si, Fe}	4.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.9
	{Fe}	3.5
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.2
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.4
	{Ca}	1.3
	{Al, Si, K}	1.2
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.0
	{Mg, Si}	0.8
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Si, Fe}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Ti}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca}	0.2
	{Ti, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{P, Ca}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.0
	{Si, Cl}	0.0
	{S, Ca}	0.0
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	1.9
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.5
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	3.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.0
Carbon rich - other	0.6
Cement or BOF converter	1.1
Cement	7.5
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.6
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	61.1
Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	23.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	1.9
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.5
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	3.5
Site - carbon-rich other	0.0
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	0.6
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.1
Urban	8.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	61.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	23.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 18b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0000
	{Si}	69.0
	{Al, Si}	7.2
	{Si, Ca LoP}	5.3
	{Si, Fe}	3.2
	{Ca}	2.8
	{Fe}	2.6
	{Si, Ca HiP}	2.1
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.5
	{Al, Si, K}	1.2
	{Mg, Si}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Si, Fe}	0.5
	{Na, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, S}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.2
	{Mg, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
	{Si, P}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.0
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Si, Cl}	0.0
	{S, Ca}	0.0
	{Ca, Ti}	0.0
	{Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Ti, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.1
Pellet	0.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.8
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.9
Carbon rich - other	1.2
Cement or BOF converter	0.3
Cement	13.8
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	51.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	22.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.3
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.1

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.8
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.1
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.8
Site - carbon-rich other	0.9
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.2
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.3
Urban	14.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	51.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	22.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.1

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 18c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0013
	{Si}	70.2
	{Al, Si}	7.7
	{Si, Ca LoP}	4.3
	{Si, Fe}	3.0
	{Fe}	2.4
	{Ca}	2.0
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.9
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.8
	{Al, Si, K}	0.9
	{Al}	0.8
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Mg, Si}	0.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Ti}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.3
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, P}	0.1
	{Mg, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.0
	{Zn-LA1}	0.0
	{Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Na, Al}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Cl}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.1
Pellet	0.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	4.4
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.4
Carbon rich - other	1.5
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	10.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	55.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	25.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

141 μm

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.4
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.3
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	4.4
Site - carbon-rich other	0.4
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	1.5
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	10.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	55.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	25.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.2

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels